

To What Extent Are Undercover Policing Practices Ethically Justifiable and Effectively Regulated in the UK?

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16039709 | ISSN: 2977-1676

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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16039709>

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The Journal of
Crime & Justice
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Acknowledgements

I am deeply grateful to my supervisor, Vanessa, for her patience and guidance during the research and writing process. I am also thankful for all her help and support over the last three years. I still remember crying happily the first year after receiving her feedback.

A massive thank you to Angie for encouraging me to pursue this topic. Her confirmation that this is a serious and relevant issue in modern policing played a key role in shaping the focus of this dissertation. Also, I appreciate her dedication and efforts to help us understand contemporary problems in the criminal justice system. She inspires us to believe that while we can't change the whole system, we can still make a positive difference, "even if it is supporting one victim".

My special thanks go to my friends Liliana and Joselyn for the mutual support we shared throughout this journey, regardless of our age differences.

Finally, I would like to thank my family for their continuous help and support.

Abstract

Examining the ethical and legal foundations of undercover policing, this library-based research investigates the extent to which covert police practices in the United Kingdom are ethically justifiable and effectively regulated. It focuses on the role of undercover officers (UCOs) and covert human intelligence sources (CHIS), both used in investigations involving organised crime, terrorism, and other serious offences. While these tactics may contribute to public safety, their use has raised long-standing concerns about abuse of power, emotional and psychological harm, and a lack of transparency. These issues raise serious questions about ethical policing practices and current regulations.

This study adopted a qualitative approach, drawing on UK legislation, official inquiries, academic literature, and policy documents. All material was ethically sourced and selected for relevance and credibility. The research is structured around two core questions: (1) to what extent can covert policing tactics be considered ethically justifiable, and (2) to what extent are they effectively regulated under UK law? These are explored through two central themes: ethical justification, assessing risk of harm, accountability, proportionality, and legal regulation, including human rights protection, supervision and transparency.

The findings show that undercover policing in the UK is only partially justifiable in practice. While covert tactics can disrupt serious and organised crime, their use often leads to emotional harm, particularly when informants are poorly managed. Officers and CHIS handlers also reported insufficient training and a lack of psychological support, raising concerns about their duty of care. Legally, the CHIS (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021 does not prohibit serious offences such as murder or torture, and the authorising bodies remain largely self-regulated. Victims are often not informed or offered redress, and there is no public transparency or accountability regarding informant spending. Because there is no disclosure, victims are deprived of their rights and unable to seek justice or understand the extent of their involvement in covert operations.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

To what extent are undercover policing practices ethically justifiable and effectively regulated in the UK? Given the word limit and the broad nature of undercover policing, this dissertation focuses specifically on the use of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) to allow for a clear and more in-depth analysis.

Undercover Police Officers (UCOs) are a covert tactic employed by law enforcement agencies to prevent and detect crime and disorder, aimed at upholding public safety. When applied correctly and supported by appropriate training, undercover policing is considered a proportionate, lawful and ethical tactic that can be effective in gathering evidence and intelligence (College of Policing, 2021). A closely related covert tool is the use of informants, now known as Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS). Early Home Office guidance, issued in 1969 and 1986, described informers as individuals who may participate in criminal activity but warned that they must not incite or assist in criminal offences (Wright, 2002).

Concerns about informants in the UK date back many years. O'Connell (1980) pointed out that keeping informants' involvement secret could affect a defendant's right to a fair trial. Courts have traditionally resisted police revelation of informants' identities. However, legal and ethical debates continue over when disclosure is necessary to ensure a fair trial. At the time, the Home Office offered some guidance, but it had no strong enforcement and only applied to police officers, not informants themselves.

A significant institutional shift in informant uses structures occurred through David Powis, who introduced a formal informant management system in response to internal police corruption. Initially piloted in Hampshire, the framework was later implemented nationwide. Trained officers acted as dedicated informant handlers, and public funds were accompanied by structured documentation and audit records. The strategy involved persuasive communications with monitoring bodies to secure discretionary payments. Over time, this led to a marked increase in individual rewards and the overall annual budget allocated to informants (Billingsley, 2009).

This dissertation critically examines the extent to which undercover policing practices in the UK are ethically justifiable and effectively regulated. It focuses specifically on the deployment of undercover

officers (UCOs) and covert human intelligence sources (CHIS), assessing both their operational value and the legal and ethical risks they pose. The analysis is structured around two core themes.

The first theme investigates: to what extent can these practices be justified in undercover policing? It highlights concerns raised in academic and policy debates, including questions of legitimacy, the psychological strain on officers, and the challenges in recruiting and managing CHIS. Ethical justifications are considered through principles such as proportionality and examined alongside critiques that point to long-term harm, the erosion of democratic values, and doubts about informants' motivation and consent. The section concludes by examining the harm and damage caused by CHIS operations, which must be considered when evaluating effectiveness, not just operational success. These include manipulated evidence, emotional impact, and supervision failings. It questions whether such harms can be ethically justified, particularly in cases involving vulnerable or marginalised individuals.

The second theme focuses on legal and regulatory issues, asking: to what extent are these practices effectively regulated in the UK? It reviews relevant legislation, regulatory frameworks, and key case studies to assess whether CHIS operations are proportionate, justified, and properly monitored. Core concerns include informant and undercover operatives' immunity, weak accountability, and blurred boundaries around acceptable conduct. Scholars and policymakers have expressed concern about transparency gaps and risks to fair trial rights. The section also considers human rights issues under Articles 6 and 8 of the ECHR, critiques the limited impact of public inquiries, and reflects on the emotional harm linked to covert tactics. Finally, it explores public trust and transparency, focusing on institutional failings, victim disclosure, and inconsistent monitoring. These factors reinforce the case for stronger protections and victim-centred reform.

1.2 Methodology

This dissertation adopts a qualitative, library-based methodology. As Babbie (1992, p. 90) explains, qualitative research often seeks to "explore, describe and explain," making it especially suitable for sensitive or under-researched topics. Maguire (2000, cited in Noaks and Wincup, 2004) also notes that researchers who investigate complex issues are often driven by curiosity, which, in this case, applies to the researcher. This study is derived from academic interest and personal experience with police investigation practices.

Due to the secretive nature of undercover policing and the deployment of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS), direct access to internal police data or participants is limited. The law protects CHIS identities, as well as institutional confidentiality, which limits transparency (Cohen and Taylor, 1972, cited in Jupp, 1989). These constraints led to the selection of a narrative literature review. Unlike systematic reviews, this method allows the researcher to interpret and analyse a broad range of relevant sources (Clark et al., 2021), enabling more flexibility in addressing policy, legal, and ethical issues.

Narrative reviews also facilitate the identification of key themes and theoretical frameworks (Davies, Francis, and Jupp, 2011), providing an opportunity to explore emerging and established ideas while highlighting research gaps. This approach supports the research's aim to evaluate covert policing's ethical and legislative implications.

1.3 Ethical Considerations

Although this study is entirely library-based and does not involve human participants, ethical considerations remain significant. The research follows the British Society of Criminology (2015) ethical standards and adheres to London Metropolitan University's academic policies. The researcher ensured that all sources were ethically sourced and carefully selected based on relevance, reliability, and publication standards. These include academic books, peer-reviewed journal articles, official reports, public inquiry statements, legislation, and regulatory guidance documents.

Liebling and Stanko (2001, cited in Noaks and Wincup, 2004) highlight that researchers studying criminal harm must consider the emotional and ethical implications of the topic. In this context, the researcher maintained a critical and reflective stance throughout the study, avoided bias, misrepresentation and upheld academic integrity during analysis and presentation.

1.4 Undercover Policing in the UK: Context and Critiques

The Metropolitan Police Service (MPS) was established to prevent crime, protect life and property, and maintain public order (Mayne, 1829, cited in FitzGerald et al., 2002). Peel's policing by consent philosophy envisioned legitimacy emerging from public approval and cooperation, through a professional police force (Shearing, 1997, cited in Garland and Sparks, 2000). Since the 1960s, crime prevention has become more intelligence-led and risk-focused, with a rise in surveillance and multi-agency strategies. Some argue that community policing was used to covertly collect local intelligence, raising concerns about low-level data collection and the erosion of traditional Peelian values (Lidstone and Palmer, 1996).

Policing has shifted from reactive responses to proactive, intelligence-driven models, especially in tackling organised crime. These approaches rely on planning, analysis, and intelligence-led case-building (Antonopoulos & Papanicolaou, 2018). Intelligence is defined as "smart information" for harm prevention (Stanko, 2009, p. 227), though its reliability depends on context and interpretation (James, 2016).

A central part of intelligence-led policing is undercover operatives (UCOs), who are trained officers authorised to gather intelligence through covert means (College of Policing, 2024d). Separately, the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act (RIPA) governs the use of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS), who form or maintain relationships for the covert purpose of obtaining or disclosing information. The Covert Human Intelligence Sources (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021 further authorises criminal conduct by CHIS under strict conditions (UK Parliament, 2021).

While UCOs and CHIS overlap in function, they are distinct roles with different legal definitions and authority to supervise. UCOs undergo rigorous psychological vetting and covert methods training. College of Policing (2024d) categorises them into UCFs (foundation), UCAs (advanced), and UCOLs (online).

O'Reilly (2022) highlights that legitimacy in policing depends not just on fairness or procedural justice but also on the perceived moral compatibility between the police and the communities they serve. However, her research shows that it is rarely straightforward. Drawing on political realism, O'Reilly (2022) argues that value conflicts between police priorities and public expectations are inevitable.

The principle of "Neither Confirm Nor Deny" (NCND) is employed by law enforcement agencies to protect covert tactics, sensitive information, and the identities of sources, including undercover officers (College of Policing, 2021, p. 34). NCND is not intended to conceal information that a force does not wish to disclose. Instead, it protects operational methods and officers' safety (ibid). Curran (2023) highlights the significant psychological strain and emotional burden undercover roles can place on officers. Drawing from interviews with former UCOs, the study found that many experienced anxieties, identity confusion, and **isolation**, especially when their support from the organisation was inconsistent or insufficient.

Based on interviews with 14 CHIS controllers across various police forces in England and Wales, Boyle (2022) identifies practical issues in the current recruitment and accreditation of CHIS handlers. His recommendations include: introducing pre-selection assessments; reducing reliance on paper applications; removing rigid HR barriers; establishing a pool of level-two trained staff; encouraging regional collaboration for training delivery; adopting a national portfolio to facilitate training development; expanding access to H1 courses; increasing operational staff input into course design; cautiously exploring psychometric testing; and promoting national coordination via the National Source Working Group. He also called for lifting restrictions on CID detectives transferring into CHIS roles.

Stanier, Nunan, and May (2024) examined the effectiveness of intelligence collection (HUMINT) and the generation of covert human intelligence sources (CHIS) during cell approaches during an exploratory study. Over a three-month period, they observed 102 cell approaches, comparing 54 conducted by dedicated intelligence officers with 48 by detectives in an English police custody suite.

The study found that detectives were notably more successful than dedicated intelligence officers in obtaining valuable intelligence and making CHIS referrals. Furthermore, the detainee's motivation to share intelligence was closely linked to factors such as revenge and lifestyle. Detainees demonstrated increased willingness to engage post-charge rather than pre-charge. Interestingly, the study also found that neither the time of day nor the detainee's age significantly influenced the success rate of intelligence gathering during cell approaches (Stanier, Nunan, and May 2024).

While undercover officers (UCOs) continue to play a critical role in serious crime investigations, they face significant psychological pressures due to long-term covert deployments, with inconsistent organisational support increasing wellbeing risks (Curran, 2023). At the same time, CHIS operations are affected by weak recruitment systems and lack of national coordination. Boyle's (2022) recommendations reveal gaps in handler accreditation, training access, and structural consistency

across forces. However, the Stanier, Nunan, and May (2024) study demonstrates that intelligence can be gathered effectively through proportionate, less intrusive alternatives, challenging the necessity of covert methods.

1.5 Understanding Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS)

The term "informant" refers to the bureaucratic designation for Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) (Clark, 2007, p. 432). Under the Police (Conduct) Regulations 2020, an informant is legally defined as "a person who provides information to an investigation on the basis that the person's identity is not disclosed during the disciplinary proceedings" (The Police (Conduct) Regulations 2020, Regulation 2(1)).

Harfield and Harfield (2013) outline a widely accepted five-part framework for determining whether someone qualifies as a CHIS. The first two tests assess whether a person establishes or maintains a relationship (personal or otherwise) and whether that relationship is covert, meaning that the other party is unaware of its true purpose. If either condition is met, the assessment proceeds to three further criteria: whether the relationship is used to obtain, access, or disclose information without the other party's knowledge. Meeting any of these criteria confirms CHIS status and triggers formal authorisation and supervision. The authors argue that protecting operational integrity and individual rights depends not on the informant's identity or outcome. Instead, it depends on the covert nature of the relationship and its adherence to statutory protections. Their framework clarifies the distinction between lawful intelligence gathering and unauthorised surveillance, preventing misuse of vague terms like "confidential source" or "tasked witness," which lack legal recognition (Harfield & Harfield, 2013, p. 133).

Despite ongoing public scepticism, informants remain essential in criminal investigations. Informers often take significant personal risks, and without their cooperation, many prosecutions would be extremely difficult to pursue. Their contributions provide vital intelligence that is otherwise inaccessible, making them an indispensable, though controversial, tool in policing (Billingsley, 2009).

Between 2017 and 2022, the number of CHIS authorisations granted to law enforcement agencies (LEA) fell dramatically from 2,651 in 2017 to 1,366 in 2022 (Investigatory Powers Commissioner's Office (IPCO) 2024). Despite this decline, the IPCO (2022) report concluded that most authorisations were legally compliant, with clear assessments of necessity and proportionality. However, it also noted a need to improve how interference is evaluated, particularly where non-target individuals' private or

family lives may be affected. Inspectors welcomed the return of in-person contact between CHIS and their handlers following COVID-19 restrictions and praised LEA efforts to assess risks such as addiction or coercion. Alongside legal compliance, CHIS welfare monitoring has become a significant concern. In several cases, officers implemented support plans and engaged external professionals to safeguard CHIS's welfare (IPCO, 2024).

Bellaby (2014) explores ethical concerns associated with bribes used in informant recruitment. He describes bribery as a practice that influences a person's decision-making without fully overriding their autonomy, since the person still has the option to refuse. This contrasts with coercive techniques like blackmail, which eliminate choice. In covert policing, this distinction matters when evaluating whether recruitment methods uphold ethical standards. Although financial incentives may seem less intrusive, they can still distort voluntary decision-making, especially if the informant is vulnerable or in financial distress. Even minor inducements can distort autonomy and should be evaluated against ethical standards rather than assumed to represent voluntary consent.

During the 2021 House of Lords debate on the CHIS (Criminal Conduct) Bill, strong concerns were raised over granting informants immunity from criminal acts. Lord Paddick, a former police officer, stated that there was no evidence of informants being unfairly prosecuted, even when examples were requested. He admitted personally handing cash to criminals in exchange for information, adding that their motivation had little to do with the public interest. The debate reflected wider concerns about whether legislation is truly necessary and adequately protects human rights (UK Parliament, 2021).

Miller (2011), in a qualitative study across five southern U.S. states, interviewed 84 former informants. He found that informant work had often become a 'moral career' marked by internal conflict, social stigma, and complicated relationships with law enforcement. Informants use psychological coping mechanisms such as neutralisation to justify their cooperation and manage the stigma of their deviant identities.

Although the latest IPCO report (2024) claimed that most CHIS authorisations were legally compliant, its only concern was CHIS welfare. Bellaby (2014) argues that even minor financial incentives can distort genuine consent, particularly when informants are vulnerable. In the House of Lords debate on the CHIS Bill, Lord Paddick observed that informants were rarely prosecuted despite their criminal activity. This raises doubts about whether legal immunity was necessary. He also stressed that informants often act out of personal interest, not public safety. Moreover, Miller's (2011) research reveals informants' long-

term emotional strain, moral conflict, and stigma. These findings call into question whether CHIS use can be ethically justified.

Chapter 2: A Critical Discussion of Undercover Policing

2.1 Ethical Frameworks

The College of Policing's Code of Ethics (2024a) applies consistently across all police forces in England and Wales. It outlines nine core principles: accountability, fairness, honesty, integrity, leadership, objectivity, openness, respect, and selflessness. Officers are expected to make responsible decisions guided by fairness, integrity, and the principle of doing the right thing for the right reasons. Accountability for both decisions and the decision-making process is fundamental. The guidelines were developed through consultation, committee input, systematic evidence review, and professional quality assurance. The review process remains ongoing and includes public consultation (College of Policing, 2024a).

Alongside the Code of Ethics, the Standards of Professional Behaviour listed in Schedule 2 of the Police (Conduct) Regulations 2020 are essential to maintaining professionalism in UK policing. These ten standards include Honesty and Integrity, Authority, Respect and Courtesy, Equality and Diversity, Use of Force, Orders and Instructions, Duties and Responsibilities, Confidentiality, Fitness for Duty, Discreditable Conduct, and Challenging and Reporting Improper Conduct. They are legally mandatory and apply to officers both on and off duty (The Police (Conduct) Regulations 2020).

The College of Policing's Practice Evidence Summary (2024b) explores how officers interpret and apply the Code in practice. Findings revealed confusion caused by the volume of guiding documents, which affected ethical decision-making. Ethical leadership was considered essential, with senior officers expected to model fair and principled behaviour. A no-blame culture was encouraged to support open discussion and learning from mistakes (College of Policing, 2024b). However, many officers viewed the Code more as a disciplinary tool than as an aspirational guide, which limited its influence. While honesty and integrity were seen as foundational, their impact was reduced by the stronger emphasis placed on the Standards of Professional Behaviour (*ibid*).

The College's Rapid Evidence Assessment of Ethical Decision-Making in Policing (2024c), conducted to inform the Code of Ethics review, examined how officers, staff, and volunteers navigate ethical dilemmas. Based on 44 studies, the review concluded that rigid rules are insufficient. Officers often face complex decisions with no clear solution, highlighting moral values. The revised principles draw on

three traditions: minimising harm, acting in line with duty and the law, and upholding traits like integrity and responsibility. Ethical conduct improves when senior leaders demonstrate fairness. Learning through peer support was also influential. However, the review noted a gap between leadership values and frontline practice. Tools and training that support self-reflection, real-world scenarios, and coping strategies were recommended, although their effectiveness remains under-evaluated. Whistleblowing and bystandership were linked to individual honesty and a supportive workplace culture (College of Policing, 2024c).

Murphy (2021) draws on Foucault's concept of governmentality to examine the ethical challenges of undercover policing. He argues that legal frameworks do not simply protect individual rights but actively shape behaviour by embedding power within structures such as authorisation and surveillance. According to Murphy (2021), rights become conditional and subject to negotiation, serving to reinforce compliance rather than protect individual autonomy. He further suggests that these dynamic challenges traditional ethical models, which assume a clear separation between the state and the individual. As a result, warns that even when covert operations are legally authorised, they may still lack ethical justification.

Curran (2021) examines the psychological impact of undercover policing. Interviews with former covert officers revealed extensive experiences of anxiety, fear, and identity pressure. Officers described isolation, secrecy within their families, and difficulty separating their real and undercover identities. The study also found that institutional support was often inadequate or absent.

The Code of Ethics and Standards of Professional Behaviour are mandatory across all police roles, including undercover officers (UCOs). These frameworks set minimum expectations for ethical conduct and professionalism and apply to all operational staff. However, College of Policing reports highlight system-wide issues, including inconsistent leadership, limited training, and confusion around ethical decision-making. These problems affect all departments but are likely to impact covert units more severely, given the complexity of their work. Murphy (2021) argues that legal frameworks often serve institutional control rather than individual care, embedding power into systems like authorisation and surveillance. Curran's (2021) research revealed concerns about the duty of care owed to officers in high-risk, emotionally demanding roles. UCOs are individuals, not just operatives of the system. When formal systems and processes fail, they are affected personally and professionally.

2.2 Purpose and Ethical Justifications of Covert Policing

Before modern policing, criminal investigations in Britain lacked formal structures and were managed through local common law or state-level prosecution. Early intelligence methods, such as those employed by Sir Francis Walsingham under Elizabeth I, used informant networks for political control (Bellamy, 1973, cited in Wright, 2002).

In current policing, informants are regularly used in covert operations, particularly in organised crime investigations. Their links to criminal networks make them useful sources of intelligence (Antonopoulos & Papanicolaou, 2018). However, their use raises ethical dilemmas. Innes (2000) notes that cost-efficiency pressures have expanded informant use, sometimes under inadequate supervision. This can damage organisational credibility and public trust, especially when informants have criminal backgrounds or conflicting interests (Abadinsky, 2017).

Maguire and John (1995) observed that intelligence from informants was often used for quick arrests rather than dismantling criminal networks. Moffett et al. (2022) agree that although CHIS operations lead to arrests, weapons seizures, and safeguarding, ethical complexity persists due to issues of motivation, coercion, and risk.

Deception is one of the core elements of policing, which involves strategies such as interviewing and resource deployment. Deception is justified when addressing serious threats, such as organised crime, where covert tactics are often necessary to prevent harm. Surveillance is an alternative to deception, but it can still mislead targets about whether they are being watched. Surveillance is often more effective as an intelligence tool when subjects do not realise they are being monitored (Nathan 2022).

Marx (1988, cited in Neyroud and Beckley, 2002, p.125) argued that the social contract theory could justify “ethical deception”. The public consents to a certain extent to deceptive practices in policing, which are in the public’s interest. This aligns with utilitarianism, where deception is justified if it serves significant purposes, such as crime prevention. However, some argue that there are situations where it is essential to preserve life; for example, when dealing with kidnappings, an ethical deception approach from law enforcement may be appropriate (Neyroud and Beckley, 2002).

Skolnick (1975, cited in Neyroud and Beckley 2002) distinguishes between investigative deception, which is sometimes permissible but not during trials or interviews. Similarly, the ECHR does not tolerate exceptions to the right to a fair trial, even though it permits minimal intervention in private life.

Additionally, Delattre (1989, cited in Neyroud and Beckley, 2002) highlights that deception's moral complexity necessitates distinct boundaries, like prohibitions on force and entrapment, over which ethical and legal norms should govern.

Murphy (2021) argues that necessity often overrides rights-related concerns. Crimes such as drug trafficking, terrorism, and corruption legitimise intrusive practices, including deception and surveillance. These methods, while effective, raise ethical questions about whether the ends justify the means. In many cases, covert policing is authorised based on broad assumptions about risk rather than specific, imminent threats. He highlights how this precautionary logic contributes to a shift in policing priorities.

Nathan (2022, p.15) explores the ethical complexity of covert policing by addressing the “*prima facie*” wrongs associated with deception, manipulation, intrusion, and direct harm. While such actions may be justified by broader social aims, they carry significant moral weight and should not be dismissed lightly. He highlights the psychological and emotional trauma that covert tactics can cause, particularly in cases involving prolonged infiltration and intimate relationships. Nathan (2022) outlines three justification models, instrumental, consent-based, and pluralist, each offering different thresholds for ethical acceptability. The instrumental model allows covert tactics if the anticipated public benefits outweigh the harms. However, he warned that excessive reliance on this model risks normalising intrusions and reducing democratic principles. Also, he advocates for a framework based on proportionality, accountability, and ongoing ethical scrutiny.

Griffin’s (2021) qualitative study of UK environmental activists reveals how covert tactics extend beyond legal consequences, causing long-term psychological and relational damage. First, he identifies ontological uncertainty as the destabilisation of individuals' trust in others and understanding of reality after discovering they have been deceived. Second, betrayal often derails their activism. Some abandon the movement entirely or redirect their efforts to surveillance reform. Yet some show resilience, adapting to their activism despite the trauma.

Moffett et al. (2022) state that even where informant use appears effective, contributing to thousands of arrests, weapons seizures, and safeguarding efforts, such outcomes must be considered alongside the complexities of managing cooperation, motivation, and deception. Officers frequently work with individuals with personal agendas, vulnerabilities, and criminal involvement, making ethical risks even higher. Moffett et al. (2022) argue that while CHIS deployment may be justified under the principle of

necessity, it still requires robust safeguarding and nuanced ethical reasoning to avoid exploitation or misconduct.

Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) have been presented by the UK Government as highly effective tools for preventing and detecting serious crime. In 2018, CHIS operations enabled the National Crime Agency to disrupt over 30 threats to life. They safeguarded more than 200 individuals and seized more than 3,000kg of Class A drugs. Metropolitan Police operations have resulted in over 3,500 arrests and the recovery of more than 100 firearms and 400 other weapons. These statistics indicate a strong contribution to public safety, particularly in counter-terrorism and serious organised crime (Home Office, 2021). Also, the same factsheet that praises these outcomes states that criminal conduct by CHIS must be necessary and proportionate (ibid).

Murphy's (2021) ethical concern is that normalised exceptions turn extraordinary powers into routine investigative tools. Moffett et al. (2022) acknowledge operational results like arrests and safeguarding but stress that ethical risks, such as motivation, coercion, and informant vulnerability, require stronger safeguarding. Nathan (2022) and Griffin (2021) highlight how covert tactics cause lasting psychological harm to targets, informants, and officers. Yet, the current framework offers no clear limits or protections. CHIS effectiveness should not be measured solely by operational outcomes but by how well regulatory frameworks uphold ethical standards. Additionally, deception in covert policing contradicts principles in the College of Policing's Code of Ethics and Standards of Professional Behaviour.

2.3 Assessing Risk and Harm in Covert Policing

The Lindop Committee report in 1978 distinguished between criminal intelligence and criminal information. Criminal information includes previous convictions and identity records-names and birth dates. Intelligence, by contrast, can be generated from assumptions, suspicions, and incomplete reports. However, such intelligence may be used without proper supervision and manipulated for purposes beyond crime prevention. The GLC Police Committee (1986) warned that unsupervised intelligence use could lead to abuse, discrimination, and wrongful surveillance (GLC Police Committee, 1986).

Building on these concerns, Hadjimatheou (2017) highlights how scandals in UK undercover policing, such as officers engaging in intimate relationships and using deceased children's identities, led to a national inquiry. The inquiry faces tensions between openness and undercover secrecy. Victims of

suspected police misconduct argue that disclosure is necessary for justice, while police claim secrecy protects officers and operations.

Historical and recent research (e.g., Marx 1988; Sharpe 2002, cited in Clarke 2007) shows informants, motivated by financial or legal incentives, may cross ethical lines or fabricate evidence to maintain their role or benefits. Police's reliance on individuals with criminal backgrounds (e.g., criminals-turned-informants) is hazardous, as these informants may manipulate the relationship for personal gain or push officers to cross legal boundaries (Sanders & Young, 2003, cited in Clarke, 2007). Cases have shown false accusations by informants are resulting in wrongful convictions (Newfield, 1979, cited in Abadinsky, 2017).

The use of informants raises ethical and practical issues, especially when their testimony is used in court, creating conflict between operational secrecy and the right to a fair trial. Their credibility is often questionable, as informants may act under pressure or for personal benefit. While they are vital in combating organised crime and terrorism, the growth of digital surveillance calls for strict regulation to protect privacy (Clarke, 2007). Additionally, promises of leniency can be misleading, as only prosecutors or courts can grant such concessions (Department of Justice, cited in Abadinsky, 2017).

Furthermore, using the informant, UCOs have access to a dangerous and lucrative underworld. There is always a chance that the law enforcement officer could become the informant's friend, coworker, boss, or partner in such a situation. In addition to improving his or her work record by capturing rival or unaffiliated criminals, the agent may be rewarded with cash and narcotics or paid for failing to apprehend traffickers or gamblers. From using criminals as informants to doing business with them, it is sometimes just a minor step (Abadinsky, 2017).

Consequently, drug enforcement is prone to corruption, often described as “secretive, duplicitous, and quasi-legal” (Manning & Redlinger, 1979, cited in Newburn, 1999, p.26). Gathering evidence can push officers into risky behaviours, such as drug use or purchases. Given the large financial stakes, bribery is a recurring threat, placing drug enforcement at the “invitational edge of corruption” (Newburn, 1999, p.27).

Farkas (1986, cited in Hibler, 2004) identified key stressors: strained supervisory relationships, the demands of undercover roles, and personal life disruption. These pressures can alter officers' views on laws, increase sympathy for offenders, and cause internal value conflicts. Psychological issues may arise even after five months in-role, and 42% of officers struggle when transitioning to other positions.

Effective undercover work demands detailed planning, support teams, and mental health guidance (Hibler, 2004).

Undercover officers undergo extensive training, including psychological assessments, ethical guidance, and legal instruction, to ensure their actions remain within clear regulatory limits (College of Policing, 2024). Informants, by contrast, receive no formal preparation.

Informants sometimes report on other informants, creating a loop of selective disclosure. This can lead to selective prosecution, where authorities choose whom to prosecute based on informant cooperation, fuelled by corruption in high-value crimes like trafficking (Eddy, Sabogal, and Walden, 1988, cited in Abadinsky, 2017).

Loftus, Feilzer, and Goold (2024) highlight the long-term psychological and emotional fallout experienced by individuals subjected to covert policing, including identity disruption, fractured relationships, and loss of trust in institutions. The authors argue for a re-evaluation of the harm beyond privacy violations, framing these impacts as hidden injuries of surveillance which fundamentally alter a person's sense of self and social belonging. Equally important is their insistence that future evaluations of covert policing should prioritise the lived experiences of those subjected to surveillance. This includes recognition of the disproportionate harms inflicted on marginalised communities and political activists.

Covert policing carries serious risks of ethical misconduct, especially when intelligence is unsupervised or based on suspicion rather than fact (Lindop Committee, 1978, cited GLC Police Committee, 1986). Informants, often acting in self-interest, can cause false accusations, wrongful convictions, and blur the lines between officers and criminals (Marx, 1988; Sharpe, 2002, cited in Clarke, 2007; Abadinsky, 2017). In addition to these operational risks, disproportionate harms frequently fall on marginalised communities (Loftus, Feilzer and Goold, 2024). While officers receive formal training (College of Policing, 2024), informants do not. Drug enforcement work operates in a secretive and loosely regulated environment, making it especially vulnerable to corruption (Manning and Redlinger, 1979, cited in Newburn, 1999). Officers may develop improper relationships with informants for personal gain (Abadinsky, 2017). Using their testimony in court raises serious concerns about reliability, fairness, and the risk of miscarriages of justice (Clarke, 2007; Department of Justice, cited in Abadinsky, 2017). This raises a crucial question: are these practices truly justifiable, and are the risks and harms they produce proportionate to the outcomes they aim to achieve?

2.4 Regulation of Undercover Policing Practices, Legal Frameworks

Informants play a crucial role in proactive criminal investigations, providing intelligence to law enforcement agencies. The Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act (RIPA) 2000 defines the legal framework for the use of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS), including informants and undercover operatives. The Investigatory Powers Act (IPA) 2016 covers powers such as interception and equipment interference (Davies, 2020). Informants provide information about criminal activity and must be deployed under strict authorisation and monitoring protocols (Hartfield and Hartfield, 2013). Section 26(8) of the RIPA 2000 legally defines CHIS and underpins the authorisation process. The revised CHIS Code of Practice reflects changes introduced by the Covert Human Intelligence Sources (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021.

This Act formally introduced Criminal Conduct Authorisations (CCAs), allowing CHIS to engage in criminal activity under specific conditions. The Code also includes strengthened safeguarding for juveniles and vulnerable adults and was informed by public consultation to address concerns regarding supervision, accountability, and proportionality (Home Office, 2022).

Under UK legislation, authorisation for the use of a CHIS may only be granted when it is considered necessary and proportionate to specific public interests. These include protecting national security, preventing or detecting crime, maintaining public order, safeguarding public health and safety, ensuring economic stability, or enabling tax collection. Further grounds may be added through official government orders (UK Government, 2021).

However, concerns were raised during parliamentary debates, with the Labour Party warning that the Act enables self-authorisation by public authorities. They advocated for prior judicial supervision to ensure independent accountability, which was not included in the final legislation (House of Lords Library, 2021).

The Covert Human Intelligence Sources (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021 grants legal immunity to both informants and their police handlers, shielding them from civil and criminal liability for authorised conduct. A key distinction between UK legislation and similar frameworks in countries such as Canada is the absence of an explicit list of prohibited offences, including serious crimes such as murder and torture. This has raised concerns about potential legal abuse and fundamental rights erosion (Scott, 2022).

The urgency for reform was underscored by the de Silva report (2012, cited in Scott 2022) on the murder of Belfast solicitor Pat Finucane, which found that various strands of state involvement had actively contributed to and facilitated his killing by loyalist paramilitaries. Before the 2021 Act, there was no statutory clarity on the liability of handlers or informants, leaving them vulnerable to prosecution under legislation such as the Accessories and Abettors Act 1861. The lack of statutory clarity created operational and legal uncertainty, as existing authorisation practices had no formal legal basis. This prompted the government to introduce a statutory framework through the 2021 Act to establish and regulate authorised criminal conduct (Scott 2022).

Following the implementation of the Covert Human Intelligence Sources (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021, the Investigatory Powers Commissioner's Office (IPCO) increased its scrutiny of Criminal Conduct Authorisations (CCAs), raising concerns about the scope of some authorisations and introducing tighter monitoring procedures. Notably, the updated Code of Practice now requires the IPCO to be notified within seven days of authorising a vulnerable adult or juvenile CHIS, ensuring early-stage protection is reviewed (IPCO, 2024).

According to IPCO's guidance, relevant disclosures include "the unlawful use of Investigatory Powers," "a failure to comply with the law or codes of practice," or "unauthorised participation in criminal activity" (IPCO, 2022, p. 2). However, in 2022, "no new disclosures of information were made to IPCO," despite the release of new guidance titled "*Disclosing Information to IPCO*", which was published to clarify how concerns should be reported (Investigatory Powers Commissioner's Office, 2024, p. 21).

Similarly, Clark (2004) warns that vague authorisations and prosecutorial discretion under RIPA risk breaching Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights, as conduct not clearly defined in law may violate privacy protections.

Schlembach (2024) discusses the case of undercover officer Mark Kennedy, whose infiltration of a protest group was not disclosed to the defence during trial proceedings. This omission ultimately led the Court of Appeal to invalidate several convictions, finding them to be unconstitutional. The case highlights the serious legal repercussions that can result from the prioritisation of operational secrecy over transparency in the justice process. The case also highlights the ethical tension between maintaining the confidentiality of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) and upholding a defendant's right to a fair trial, particularly when the role of undercover officers remains hidden from the courts.

Baroness Chakrabarti, a prominent human rights advocate, led the opposition in the House of Lords. She warned that the CCA (2021) would grant total criminal and civil immunity for undercover operatives and allow them to commit unlimited crimes in advance with no consequence after the fact. In her view, such power went far beyond formalising existing practice and represented a dangerous expansion of government authority. She argued that rather than offering agents blanket legal protection, the public interest defences already familiar with UK law should be sufficient to protect agents acting in good faith. In addition, she maintained that no agent had been unfairly prosecuted under the previous system (UK Parliament, 2021).

In 1995, before the introduction of the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act (2000), there were an estimated 43,000 authorised Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) operating in England and Wales (Billingsley et al., 2001, cited in Stanier and Nunan, 2025). However, since the implementation of the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act (2000), authorisation figures have declined significantly. By 2001, the number of authorised CHIS had fallen to 5,900 across all law enforcement agencies, representing an 86% reduction. More recent figures show that by 2018, only 1,958 CHIS had been authorised by law enforcement agencies (IPCO, 2022). Stanier and Nunan (2025) argue that this decline is due to a complex interplay of factors, with two key issues emerging: the impact of budget cuts and a pervasive culture of fear and risk within agencies.

In 2017, there were 2,651 authorised Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS) across UK law enforcement agencies (IPCO, 2024, p. 61). In the same financial year (2017/18), the Metropolitan Police Service spent £879,676 on payments to informants. By 2022, the number of authorised CHIS had reduced to 1,366, while spending increased to £1,041,442.60 in the 2022/23 financial year (Metropolitan Police Service, 2023).

Although the CHIS (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021 provides formal authorisation for criminal conduct, its failure to prohibit serious offences such as murder or torture exposes fundamental regulatory weaknesses (Scott, 2022). Furthermore, the lack of judicial control means authorising bodies are largely self-regulating, reducing transparency and external accountability (House of Lords Library, 2021). Metropolitan Police data shows that over £1 million was spent on informants in a year. While we cannot determine how many CHIS authorisations were issued by the Met specifically, their spending has increased. However, there is no transparency or public accountability regarding how taxpayer money is used.

2.5 Human Rights and Undercover Policing

Law enforcement agencies in the UK often use prosecution discretion to avoid charging informants involved in criminal conduct. This discretion, exercised by the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS), is legally permitted under Section 2(14) (Lidstone and Palmer, 1996). However, Clark (2004) warned that broad and ambiguous authorisations risk enabling actions that go beyond the original scope intended by authorising officers. These practices may conflict with the legal requirement to comply with the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), particularly Article 8, which safeguards the right to privacy.

Schlembach (2024) highlights the dual nature of public inquiries, explaining that while they may appear to offer justice and institutional accountability, they are often compromised by political framing and a lack of legal force. In the case of the Undercover Policing Inquiry, public frustration grew as its conclusions failed to result in meaningful policy change. Schlembach (2024) argues that inquiries can serve as state-led performances managing dissent rather than resolving it, drawing participants into symbolic processes despite their deep mistrust of the institutions involved.

The Undercover Policing Inquiry (2025) revealed significant breaches of civil liberties. In one example, an officer identified as RFN2 engaged in a sexual relationship with a woman referred to as 'Gabriella' while deployed undercover. This resulted in a child's birth. The Inquiry granted anonymity to RFN2 to protect Gabriella and her child's right to private and family life under Article 8 ECHR. RFN26, who supervised the Avon and Somerset Special Tactics Unit responsible for RFN2's deployment, denied any knowledge of the relationship until after his retirement in 2013. Nevertheless, the Inquiry determined that RFN26 could still provide relevant evidence under a pseudonym (Undercover Policing Inquiry, 2025).

These issues raise broader concerns about government accountability and access to redress in covert misconduct. Although the Government argues that CHIS can claim compensation via the Investigatory Powers Tribunal, Lord Anderson of Ipswich highlighted practical barriers that prevent informants from knowing their rights to seek compensation (UK Parliament, 2021). For the police, a significant portion of what the public perceives as a violation of civil liberties has been framed as a necessary response to oppressive and unnecessary restrictions on the "fight against crime" (Jefferson and Grimshaw, 1984, p. 4).

Moreover, Bonino and Kaoullas (2015) argue that intelligence collection aimed at political expression rather than criminal activities blurs the boundary between law enforcement and political surveillance. Such practices threaten the right to protest and put at risk the principle of policing by consent. The issue is particularly serious when intelligence is collected from individuals engaged in lawful activities.

Murphy (2021) offers a critical view of how undercover policing is regulated, particularly in the UK. He argues that legislation such as RIPA appears to offer safeguards through strict codes of practice, but these often serve more to legitimise covert government action than to constrain it. He critiques the Revised Code of Practice for Human Intelligence Sources (2018) for outlining expectations without providing mechanisms to enforce them meaningfully. As a result, covert policing can operate within a legal grey area, where formal structures exist but real accountability is limited. He further argues that such vague and inconsistently applied monitoring erodes public trust in the law's ability to safeguard freedoms. Without rigorous enforcement and independent supervision, human rights risk becoming symbolic rather than substantive, especially in contexts involving powerful and secretive policing practices.

Article 8 of the ECHR protects privacy, family life, home, and correspondence. It permits interference only under certain conditions, such as national security or crime prevention. To be compliant, CHIS deployment must be legitimate, necessary, and proportionate. The concept of by the law requires precise legal boundaries defining when and how surveillance is justified, including clear identification of individuals and offences subject to surveillance, alongside sufficient protection against abuse. Proportionality demands that any intervention be limited and justified by the investigation's value (Clark, 2007).

Despite legislative progress, Clark (2004) highlighted a critical gap in the current legal framework. He pointed out that while covert participation in criminal activity is an established tactic, RIPA does not explicitly authorise such conduct. Instead, agencies rely on vaguely worded authorisations and prosecutorial discretion, creating ambiguity around responsibility and accountability. This discretion lies with the CPS, not the agencies themselves. Such an approach raises concerns under Article 8 ECHR, as conduct not clearly in compliance with the law risks breaching human rights (Clark, 2004).

Article 6 ECHR, guaranteeing the right to a fair trial, is equally critical. If covert operations compromise evidence integrity or procedural fairness, admissibility can be challenged. Evidence obtained in violation of Articles 6 or 8 may be declared inadmissible, particularly if resulting from entrapment or unauthorised CHIS operations. This may jeopardise trial fairness. Under the Police and Criminal Evidence Act (PACE), evidence gathered illegally or unfairly may be excluded, protecting defendants' rights. However, effective monitoring of CHIS activities remains a challenge. RIPA authorises covert investigations but has been criticised for allowing extensive discretion and relying on post-hoc reviews rather than real-time monitoring, potentially enabling abuse (Clark, 2007).

Loftus, Feilzer, and Goold (2024) highlight the damaging personal impacts of covert policing tactics. They show that undercover policing can violate privacy, create distrust in personal relationships, and harm entire communities. Importantly, they call for a shift in policy and research towards recognising not only visible harms but also the emotional and symbolic violence inflicted by prolonged covert surveillance. They advocate a human-centred, trauma-informed approach to regulation, suggesting that this is essential to restoring public trust and setting ethical limits on state power in democratic societies.

Scholars like Clark (2004) and Murphy (2021) highlight those vague authorisations and weak governance under RIPA risk breaching Article 8 ECHR. Schlembach (2024) questions whether these inquiries truly deliver accountability, especially in cases like Gabriella's, which exposed severe privacy violations. Bonino and Kaoullas (2015) reveal how surveillance has extended to peaceful protesters, blurring the line between political and criminal intelligence. This trend is deeply concerning, as law enforcement should focus on serious crime, not monitoring activists.

2.6 Transparency and Public Trust

The Metropolitan Police Service (MPS) has openly acknowledged serious historical failings in its undercover policing practices, including abusive sexual relationships, poor management and control, and misuse of covert identities. Despite these issues, the MPS maintains that undercover policing remains a vital and lawful tactic when used ethically and within clear legal frameworks (Metropolitan Police Service, 2020).

The National Police Chiefs' Council (NPCC) plays a central role in shaping and monitoring policy through its National Undercover Working Group. It acknowledges past failures in undercover policing that have damaged public trust, but also highlights substantial reforms made in recent years. These reforms

included stricter legislation, clearer internal guidelines, and better systems for accountability (NPCC, 2020).

The NPCC holds a core participant status in the Undercover Policing Inquiry. It has contributed millions of documents and coordinated risk assessments in support of the inquiry process. It has expressed a commitment to transparency, learning from past mistakes, and upholding ethical standards in future undercover operations (ibid).

Hadjimatheou (2017) describes how police rely on prior arguments to justify a 'neither confirm nor deny' stance in response to disclosure requests. These arguments bypass case-specific risk assessments, even where unofficial disclosures were made. Hadjimatheou (2017) argues that such arguments apply too broadly, carry more weight than justified, and wrongly avoid detailed, case-by-case considerations.

One of the key concerns surrounding the Covert Human Intelligence Sources (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021 is the lack of transparency for victims affected by undercover operations. During a House of Lords debate, Lord Anderson of Ipswich raised the issue of how victims can be informed that they were harmed by a CHIS, particularly if their injuries resulted from an authorised offence. If the victims are never told that an undercover officer was involved, they may not seek compensation or justice. Although some mechanisms exist, such as through the Investigatory Powers Tribunal or the Criminal Injuries Compensation Scheme, the secrecy surrounding these operations means victims are unlikely to realise they have been affected. This lack of disclosure prevents individual justice but also reduces public trust in policing and accountability (UK Parliament, 2021).

A crucial ethical issue remains: how can victims know they were harmed by a UCO if no disclosure is made? The current system may prevent victims from knowing their rights have been violated. Unlike Germany, which has implemented legislation granting individuals access to records concerning their surveillance once state monitoring concludes (Joubert, 1994, cited in Loftus, Feilzer, and Goold, 2024), the UK offers no such automatic disclosure or redress. This procedural gap ensures that individuals subjected to misconduct or disproportionate CHIS activity may never learn of it. As Lord Anderson of Ipswich asked during the House of Lords debate, how can victims seek compensation or legal remedy if they are never informed that a CHIS was involved (UK Parliament, 2021).

The ITV documentary *The Undercover Police Scandal: Love and Lies Exposed* (2025) reveals how over 60 women were deceived into long-term relationships with undercover officers, some having children.

These relationships were part of broader strategies by secret police units to monitor activism and protest between 1960 and 2011. Speaking publicly for the first time, women described themselves as seduced, manipulated, and abruptly abandoned. Most received similar letters from officers who had vanished. One case involved Alison, who had a five-year relationship with an officer posing as Mark Cassidy and planned a family with him. Only after their breakup did she learn about his identity. PC Mark Kennedy's exposure in 2011 catalysed the public inquiry now known as the Spycops Scandal. Alison described their experiences as institutional abuse used to weaken progressive movements, calling for greater accountability and legal reform (ITV, 2025).

Carson (2010) argues that while professionals such as surgeons can be sued for errors, police detectives in the UK are legally exempt from civil claims for negligent investigations. This is unlike in countries such as Canada and South Africa. He claims that this discrepancy negatively impacts public confidence in law enforcement and is becoming increasingly problematic. Carson suggests that allowing civil lawsuits against detectives could encourage a culture of accountability and continuous learning within police departments. He maintains that potential risks, such as perceptions of increased liability or resource diversion, can be mitigated through carefully crafted legislative reforms. Ultimately, he concludes that legal reform is necessary to align policing with broader public expectations of professional responsibility and transparency.

Recent inspections by the Investigatory Powers Commissioner's Office (IPCO) continue to raise concerns about the operational handling of Covert Human Intelligence Sources (CHIS). A December 2022 inspection found that several issues flagged in earlier reports had still not been fully addressed. These included incomplete individual risk assessments for CHIS, unclear descriptions of authorised conduct by Authorising Officers, and insufficient detail provided in activity reviews (IPCO, 2024).

Despite these ongoing issues, the report also notes improvements in the specificity and quality of directed surveillance records. In addition, it notes the introduction of an IT system designed to centralise CHIS case records. Although still in development, this system is expected to improve access and record-keeping for future inspections (IPCO, 2024). Furthermore, the report highlights that GCHQ has begun using the CHIS Criminal Conduct Authorisation (CCA) powers introduced by the 2021 Act, with high standards observed in their internal authorisations (IPCO, 2024).

Atkinson (2019) highlights that assessing informant coverage, the extent to which CHIS provide useful intelligence on targets, suspects, and criminal activity, varies significantly across law enforcement. This variation stems from a lack of a standard methodology and is often shaped by operational judgment

rather than consistent analytical frameworks. These inconsistencies raise concerns about the reliability, accountability, and effectiveness of informant deployment, especially when decisions lack clear evaluative criteria. Also, he stresses the emerging yet underused role of intelligence analysts in enhancing CHIS' strategic value, suggesting that without proactive leadership and structured monitoring, informant use risks becoming opaque and ethically questionable.

Despite institutional acknowledgements of past failures, transparency in undercover policing remains superficial. Policies like neither confirm nor deny (Hadjimatheou, 2017) and secrecy around CHIS authorisations (UK Parliament, 2021) block victim redress and shield misconduct. Evidence from the ITV documentary shows that the long-term deception was not accidental but systematic, targeting political activism. These practices damage public trust and reinforce calls for reform to ensure legal accountability and ethical policing to protect victims (Carson, 2010).

Chapter 3: Conclusion

This dissertation exposed the following problematic issues about undercover policing and how practices are regulated in the UK. Firstly, the roles, functions, and challenges of undercover officers (UCOs) and covert human intelligence sources (CHIS) were identified, highlighting their operational importance and the personal, ethical, and structural concerns linked to their deployment.

Long-term covert deployments put undercover officers (UCOs) under significant psychological strain, and their well-being is at risk due to insufficient organisational support. Inadequate national coordination and inconsistent recruitment processes impact CHIS activities. Significant deficiencies were found in handler accreditation, training availability, and structural uniformity across forces. Moreover, the increasing need for covert tactics should prompt reflection on whether intelligence could be obtained more ethically and effectively through proportionate, less intrusive methods.

Financial incentives can distort an informant's genuine consent, especially when the individual is vulnerable. Despite their criminal activities, informants were rarely prosecuted, raising questions about whether legal immunity was appropriate. Moreover, they often act in their own interests rather than the public's. Research shows that informants experience long-term psychological strain, internal moral conflict, and lasting stigma associated with their role. These concerns directly relate to the ethical justification for CHIS use in practice.

Secondly, the ethical justifications and intended purposes of covert policing were examined, alongside a critical assessment of how risks and harms are addressed in practice. However, College of Policing reports identify systemic issues such as inconsistent leadership, insufficient training, and unclear ethical guidance. Given the complexity of their work, covert units are likely to be more severely impacted by these issues, which are widespread across policing departments.

Legal frameworks often integrate power into systems such as authorisation and monitoring, serving as institutional control rather than individual care. Concerns have been raised about the duty of care owed to officers working in emotionally taxing and high-risk roles. UCOs are not just functional agents of the system; they are individuals, and when organisational structures fail, the consequences are felt professionally and personally.

When exceptions become normalised, extraordinary powers risk becoming standard tools. While acknowledging outcomes like arrests and safeguarding, stronger protections are needed to address ethical challenges linked to coercion, informant vulnerability, and unclear motives. The framework lacks clear boundaries or safeguards and does not fully account for long-term psychological harm to informants, targets, and officers. CHIS effectiveness should be assessed by the extent to which regulations uphold ethical principles.

When intelligence relies on suspicion rather than fact, covert policing risks ethical failure. Self-interested informants may produce false leads, resulting in wrongful arrests or convictions, and further eroding the boundaries between law enforcement and criminality. Marginalised communities are especially vulnerable. While police officers undergo formal training, informants do not. Officers may form inappropriate relationships with informants for their benefit. The use of informant testimony in court raises concerns about reliability, fairness, and the potential for miscarriages of justice. It is important to address the question of whether these operations are truly justified and whether the risks and harms they cause are proportionate to the goals they aim to accomplish.

Lastly, the analysis focused on how undercover policing is regulated in the UK, including legal frameworks, human rights concerns, and transparency and public trust in these practices. Despite formally authorising criminal behaviour, the *CHIS (Criminal Conduct) Act 2021* exposes major regulatory flaws. It fails to prohibit serious offences such as murder or torture. In addition, authorising bodies remain largely self-regulated due to the absence of judicial supervision, which limits transparency and external accountability. For example, Metropolitan Police figures show that over £1 million was spent on informants in a year. Although the exact number of CHIS authorisations issued remains unclear, CHIS-related expenditures have increased. However, there is little transparency or public accountability regarding taxpayer funds.

Scholars highlight that RIPA's vague authorisation conditions and weak oversight pose serious risks to Article 8 rights under the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which protects private and family life. This raises the question of whether such investigations bring about accountability, especially in high-profile cases like Gabriella's, which exposed major violations of privacy. As surveillance practices have expanded to cover peaceful protesters and political activists, the line between criminal intelligence and political monitoring has become increasingly blurred. Also, it limits freedom of speech.

Transparency in undercover policing remains superficial, even as public institutions acknowledge past misconduct. Policies such as NCND, alongside the confidentiality surrounding CHIS authorisations,

obstruct victim redress and shield the wrongdoings from public scrutiny. This failure to notify victims obstructs individual justice and erodes public trust and accountability. This reinforces concerns that CHIS authorisations can occur without meaningful supervision or ethical recourse. Evidence from the ITV investigation indicates that long-term deception targeting political activism was not incidental but systematic.

Therefore, in response to the research question, *“To what extent are undercover policing practices ethically justifiable and effectively regulated in the UK?”*, the findings show that while covert tactics may claim serious crime disruption, current practices are partially ethically justifiable and insufficiently regulated. Victims and officers are not adequately protected, and agencies lack transparent performance reporting and information on spending.

Future research could identify alternatives for obtaining intelligence that do not place anyone at personal or psychological risk. As highlighted in this study, CHIS use raises ethical concerns and emotional harm to informants and officers. It is therefore imperative to explore intelligence methods that are more proportionate, transparent, and ethically sustainable. One promising area is artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics to detect criminal activity through behavioural patterns, communication monitoring, and predictive analysis. Research should examine whether such approaches can operate within ethical and legal boundaries. This is critical to reduce dependence on covert human sources, improve accountability, and align intelligence-gathering with modern ethical standards.

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